

Supplement Materials: Electron density and its relation with optical properties in 2D Mo/W dichalcogenides

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Table S1. Calculated lattice constants a and c and indirect bandgaps E_g of bulk MX_2 ($X=\text{S, Se, Te}$) by using WC-GGA, optB88-vdW and mBJ functionals, as well as other theoretical “(c)” and experimental “(e)” data.

MX ₂	a (Å)			c (Å)			E_g (eV)			
	WC-GGA	optB88-vdW	Calc. & Exp.	WC-GGA	optB88-vdW	Calc. & Exp.	WC-GGA	optB88-vdW	mBJ	Calc. & Exp.
MoS ₂	3.155	3.199	3.169 ^(c) [1]	14.935	14.932	12.324 ^(c) [1]	1.675	1.515	1.784	1.23 ^(c) [1]
			3.148 ^(c) [2]			12.300 ^(c) [2]				1.71 ^(c) [4]
			3.160 ^(c) [3]			12.292 ^(c) [3]				1.89 ^(c) [5]
MoSe ₂	3.280	3.338	3.289 ^(c) [1]	15.488	15.467	12.927 ^(c) [1]	1.449	1.399	1.535	1.11 ^(c) [1]
			3.299 ^(c) [6]			12.938 ^(c) [6]				1.44 ^(c) [4]
			3.288 ^(c) [3]			12.902 ^(c) [3]				1.55 ^(c) [7]
MoTe ₂	3.505	3.558	3.522 ^(c) [6]	15.364	15.412	13.968 ^(c) [6]	0.925	0.950	1.023	0.90 ^(c) [10]
			3.458 ^(c) [8]			13.294 ^(c) [8]				1.12 ^(c) [4]
			3.518 ^(c) [9]			13.974 ^(c) [9]				1.08 ^(c) [11]
			3.517 ^(c) [3]			13.822 ^(c) [3]				
WS ₂	3.159	3.202	3.153 ^(c) [1]	14.238	14.253	12.323 ^(c) [1]	1.613	1.515	1.909	1.30 ^(c) [1]
			3.138 ^(c) [12]			12.416 ^(c) [12]				1.77 ^(c) [4]
			3.154 ^(c) [3]			13.564 ^(c) [3]				1.90 ^(c) [13]
WSe ₂	3.281	3.331	3.282 ^(c) [1]	15.113	15.085	12.961 ^(c) [1]	1.440	1.427	1.600	1.19 ^(c) [1]
			3.299 ^(c) [14]			13.092 ^(c) [14]				1.54 ^(c) [4]
			3.282 ^(c) [15]			13.459 ^(c) [15]				1.65 ^(c) [16]
WTe ₂	3.508	3.573	3.510 ^(c) [17]	15.043	15.058	13.900 ^(c) [17]	0.898	0.957	1.041	0.81 ^(c) [17]
			3.600 ^(c) [18]			14.180 ^(c) [18]				0.70 ^(c) [18]

Figure S1. Band structures of bulk, mono-, bi- and tri-layered MoS₂ (a), MoSe₂ (b) and MoTe₂ (c) calculated by WC-GGA functional.

Figure S2. Band structures of bulk, mono-, bi- and tri-layered WS₂ (a), WSe₂ (b) and WTe₂ (c) calculated by WC-GGA functional.

Figure S3. Electron density (a) and Laplacian (b) distributions of bulk, mono-, bi-, and tri-layered MoS₂. Labels “b”, “r” and “c” represent bond, ring and cage critical points at the zero-flux surface respectively.

Figure S4. In-plane (*xx*) and out-of-plane (*zz*) refractive indexes *n* (a), absorption coefficients α (b) and loss tangents (c) of N¹⁻⁹ heterostructures.

Figure S5. Electron density (a) and Laplacian (b) distributions of the N¹ WS₂/MoS₂ heterostructure along the $\langle 110 \rangle$ plane (a)-(i). Labels “b”, “r” and “c” represent bond, ring and cage critical points at zero-flux surface respectively.

Reference

1. Jiang, H. Electronic band structures of Molybdenum and Tungsten dichalcogenides by the GW approach. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2012**, *116*, 7664–7671, doi:10.1021/jp300079d.
2. Young, P.A. Lattice parameter measurements on molybdenum disulphide. *J. Phys. Appl. Phys.* **1968**, *1*, 936–938, doi:10.1088/0022-3727/1/7/416.
3. Wilson, J.A.; Yoffe, A.D. The transition metal dichalcogenides discussion and interpretation of the observed optical, electrical and structural properties. *Adv. Phys.* **1969**, *18*, 193–335, doi:10.1080/00018736900101307.
4. Reyes-Retana, J.A.; Cervantes-Sodi, F. Spin-orbital effects in metal-dichalcogenide semiconducting monolayers. *Sci. Rep.* **2016**, *6*, 24093, doi:10.1038/srep24093.
5. Ji, Q.; Zhang, Y.; Gao, T.; Zhang, Y.; Ma, D.; Liu, M.; Chen, Y.; Qiao, X.; Tan, P.-H.; Kan, M.; et al. Epitaxial Monolayer MoS₂ on Mica with Novel Photoluminescence. *Nano Lett.* **2013**, *13*, 3870–3877, doi:10.1021/nl401938t.
6. Böker, Th.; Severin, R.; Müller, A.; Janowitz, C.; Manzke, R.; Voß, D.; Krüger, P.; Mazur, A.; Pollmann, J. Band structure of MoS₂, MoSe₂, and α-MoTe₂: Angle-resolved photoelectron spectroscopy and *ab initio* calculations. *Phys. Rev. B* **2001**, *64*, 235305, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.64.235305.
7. Tongay, S.; Zhou, J.; Ataca, C.; Lo, K.; Matthews, T.S.; Li, J.; Grossman, J.C.; Wu, J. Thermally Driven Crossover from Indirect toward Direct Bandgap in 2D Semiconductors: MoSe₂ versus MoS₂. *Nano Lett.* **2012**, *12*, 5576–5580, doi:10.1021/nl302584w.
8. Rano, B.R.; Syed, I.M.; Naqib, S.H. *Ab initio* approach to the elastic, electronic, and optical properties of MoTe₂ topological Weyl semimetal. *J. Alloys Compd.* **2020**, *829*, 154522, doi:10.1016/j.jallcom.2020.154522.
9. Tse, G.; Yu, D. The First Principle Study: Structural, Electronic, Optical, Phonon and Elastic Properties in Bulk and Monolayer Molybdenum Ditelluride. *J. Nanoelectron. Optoelectron.* **2017**, *12*, 89–99, doi:10.1166/jno.2017.1976.
10. Keum, D.H.; Cho, S.; Kim, J.H.; Choe, D.-H.; Sung, H.-J.; Kan, M.; Kang, H.; Hwang, J.-Y.; Kim, S.W.; Yang, H.; et al. Bandgap opening in few-layered monoclinic MoTe₂. *Nat. Phys.* **2015**, *11*, 482–486, doi:10.1038/nphys3314.
11. Chen, B.; Sahin, H.; Suslu, A.; Ding, L.; Bertoni, M.I.; Peeters, F.M.; Tongay, S. Environmental Changes in MoTe₂ Excitonic Dynamics by Defects-Activated Molecular Interaction. *ACS Nano* **2015**, *9*, 5326–5332, doi:10.1021/acsnano.5b00985.
12. Li, L.; Zeng, Z.-Y.; Liang, T.; Tang, M.; Cheng, Y. Elastic Properties and Electronic Structure of WS₂ under Pressure from First-principles Calculations. *Z. Für Naturforschung A* **2017**, *72*, 295–301, doi:10.1515/zna-2016-0398.
13. Sik Hwang, W.; Remskar, M.; Yan, R.; Protasenko, V.; Tahy, K.; Doo Chae, S.; Zhao, P.; Konar, A.; (Grace) Xing, H.; Seabaugh, A.; et al. Transistors with chemically synthesized layered semiconductor WS₂ exhibiting 10⁵ room temperature modulation and ambipolar behavior. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2012**, *101*, 013107, doi:10.1063/1.4732522.
14. Feng, L.; Li, N.; Yang, M.; Liu, Z. Effect of pressure on elastic, mechanical and electronic properties of WSe₂: A first-principles study. *Mater. Res. Bull.* **2014**, *50*, 503–508, doi:10.1016/j.materresbull.2013.11.016.
15. Reshak, A.H.; Auluck, S. Electronic and optical properties of 2H-WSe₂ intercalated with copper. *Phys. Rev. B* **2003**, *68*, 195107, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.68.195107.
16. Kozawa, D.; Kumar, R.; Carvalho, A.; Kumar Amara, K.; Zhao, W.; Wang, S.; Toh, M.; Ribeiro, R.M.; Castro Neto, A.H.; Matsuda, K.; et al. Photocarrier relaxation pathway in two-dimensional semiconducting transition metal dichalcogenides. *Nat. Commun.* **2014**, *5*, 4543, doi:10.1038/ncomms5543.
17. Kumar, A.; Ahluwalia, P.K. Electronic structure of transition metal dichalcogenides monolayers 1H-MX₂ (M = Mo, W; X = S, Se, Te) from *ab-initio* theory: new direct band gap semiconductors. *Eur. Phys. J. B* **2012**, *85*, 186, doi:10.1140/epjb/e2012-30070-x.
18. Dawson, W.G.; Bullett, D.W. Electronic structure and crystallography of MoTe₂ and WTe₂. *J. Phys. C Solid State Phys.* **1987**, *20*, 6159–6174, doi:10.1088/0022-3719/20/36/017.